

Category	Sub-category	Description	Exemplary Quotes
USAGE			
How they use it for learning	Role-based Prompting	Participants instructed genAI systems to assume a specific role (e.g., a TA) or to explain concepts to a particular type of audience (e.g., a child).	"I used to often ask ChatGPT and Bard to pretend to be my TA for the class, pretending I'm a complete novice" (P2)
	Using AI as an advanced search engine	Participants used genAI as an advanced search engine for finding resources of interest or narrowing down search space.	"I used to ask ChatGPT to get a basic idea of what all I needed to learn. If it gave me 3 things, I would then look up and read about those things" (P9)
	Combining AI responses with other sources	Participants combined genAI with other resources to gain a well-rounded understanding of concepts	"Sometimes if I want a more in depth detail I'll probably go and see if I can find something on YouTube just because if it's really specific and I need to understand all parts of it, like how does this binary search tree parsing work chatGPT is not really good at giving the complete answer here" (P16)
	Using course materials to query AI	Participants consulted class resources to ask genAI focused questions to refine or expand on their knowledge.	"I get familiarized with the jargon using class resources, and then come back to GPT and ask specific questions. I then use that knowledge to learn the concept and then apply it for my problem" (P4)
How they use it for implementations	Using AI to improve own or obtained code	Participants used genAI tools to refine their code (or the ones retrieved from other sources), for better performance and compliance with best practices	"When dealing with a problem, I use generative AI to optimize the solutions I have built. I ask it for the recommended best practices or industry standard approach for this type of problem" (P1)
	Using AI for code snippets and organizing it on their own	Participants used genAI to acquire code components which they then organize in their projects	"I lean towards using genAI for individual parts that I planned dealing with in my project, that's where I think its value comes from. [...] I can take those pieces and organize it to fit those into my project" (P3)
	Combining AI-generated code with traditional sources	Participants blended genAI-generated code with insights from traditional resources (e.g. stackoverflow) to craft effective solutions.	"I used ChatGPT for web scraping [...] and I used Mozilla developer Docs to fulfill the rest of the gaps and portions it missed" (P3)
BENEFITS			
...In Incremental Learning (L2)	Revising concepts	Participants found genAI useful for revisiting and brushing up on previously learned concepts.	"ChatGPT can help in brushing up or polishing concepts if you have a basic understanding of it" (P14)
	Obtaining descriptive examples	Participants found genAI helpful for obtaining practical examples to aid their understanding.	"You can ask generative AI to give you an example or demonstrate what you're asking about in practice, which is helpful" (P3)
	Getting practice problems	Participants found genAI useful for getting practice problems to enhance their understanding of a topic.	"I would also ask for incrementally challenging practice problems with a topic. It helped me have a practical understanding" (P1)
	Learning syntax	Participants found genAI to be useful for grasping the syntax of a new programming language, provided they were already familiar with programming	"GenAI was useful when I needed to learn a particular JS syntax. I could understand what it said because I already knew how to program in JS" (P13).
...In Initial Implementations (I1)	Comprehending code snippets	Participants found genAI beneficial for getting started with initial coding tasks, providing foundational code snippets, and setting up basic project structures.	"When genAI gives the code I ask it to give explanations about the code with a line by line comment so I can really understand what each line is actually doing" (P4)
	Brainstorming Ideas	Participants found genAI beneficial as a brainstorming tool for helping generate ideas and explore new possibilities for projects and solutions	"I think it really helps me understand better. Sometimes, when I ask ChatGPT or Bard a question, it gives me answers in ways I hadn't thought about, and I'm like oh, yeah, that's really insightful. It makes me realize things I hadn't considered before, hence broadens my knowledge." (P14)
	Finding useful resources	Participants used genAI as a starting point and identified relevant resources for useful information and materials for projects	"Given a problem or an assignment, the hardest part is to get started. AI is really helpful in that, it is useful in brainstorming, and it points you to sources that can lead you to the goal" (P4)
	Obtaining initial guidance	Participants used genAI for initial guidance in their implementations seeking instructors about what to do	"I was clueless at the start of a game development project. I asked ChatGPT how to go through developing that and it gave me basic instructions on things I needed to implement depending on my project and a couple of steps that I needed to follow" (P9)
Common Benefits across L2 and I1	Clarifying concepts and code	Participants used genAI for clarifying doubts and gaining clearer understanding of concepts	"[ChatGPT] would come in handy at times when I need help with understanding a concept or trying to learn something taught in the class" (P14)
	Personalized support	Participants used genAI in obtaining personalized help for concepts and code	"If I need a clearer explanation of a topic from class or if I am stuck with something in my code, I definitely turn to generative AI for a personalized explanation" (P12).
	Getting surface level understanding	Participants used genAI to obtain a surface level understanding of concepts or technologies they were unfamiliar with.	"I would say rely on ChatGPT to polish my understanding of a concepts, and sometimes to have a basic understanding of it" (P14)
	Getting structured outlines or roadmaps	Participants found genAI useful for getting structured outlines which aided in identifying key topics for their context.	"I find myself leaning more and more on genAI tools to get structured outlines and to know what information I need to gather" (P3)
CHALLENGES			
Unclear understanding of genAI and its use	Ethical dilemma	Participants struggled with determining the ethical boundaries and the proper use of GenAI in software engineering	"I don't know whether it is ethical to use generative AI for actual implementations" (P10)
	Setting realistic expectations	Participants reported that setting realistic expectations of genAI's capabilities was difficult.	"I know for a fact that it wasn't exactly as helpful as I thought it would be...because it did not quite match my expectation" (P14)
	Gauging genAI's Limitations	Participants found it hard to gauge the tool's effectiveness and scope accurately	"Initially, when I first started using it, I would trust it less because I wasn't quite exposed yet to how they work and how effective they actually were" (P14)
	Framing the right questions or prompts	Participants struggled to frame the right questions or prompts to elicit proper responses from genAI.	"My biggest challenge is asking it the right questions, to get a useful response out of it" (P6)

Difficulty in effectively communicating needs or context	Communicating context	Participants found it hard to communicate their needs to genAI and provide appropriate context.	<i>"The biggest challenge was providing enough context to [ChatGPT] and communicate my needs about what I'm trying to do" (P3)</i>
	Need for domain knowledge to query AI	Participants struggled to effectively use genAI as it requires domain-specific knowledge to verify the quality of its responses.	<i>"The difficulty is when there is a knowledge gap and you are using it for things without having solid fundamentals about it. If you don't understand the concept, you can't use AI for it" (P4)</i>
	Multiple back-and-forth exchanges	Engaging with genAI involved back-and-forth exchanges to refine and clarify queries to get proper response.	<i>"Sometimes it misunderstands my question and then I just go back and forth with the context till it fixes it's answers" (P7)</i>
Difficulty in aligning AI to process or preferences	Hard to align AI to preference/process	Participants struggled to get genAI to respond in ways that match their preferences or process.	<i>"[ChatGPT] does not take into account my preferences or style or what I want to fix in the codebase" (P16)</i>
	Interrupts thought process	Code generating AI tools (e.g. Copilot) disrupted participants' thought processes	<i>"[Copilot] gives huge blocks of things that you don't want and that breaks the flow and your thought process" (P7)</i>
	Hard to align with learning style	Participants struggled to match genAI's assistance to their learning styles.	<i>"Generative AI was not aligned to my style of learning [...] the way it talks to me is not the way I want to learn" (P12)</i>
Issues in obtaining proper rationales behind genAI responses	Getting proper rationales	Participants struggled to obtain clear rationales for AI-generated answers and suggested solutions	<i>If I want to know why a procedure operates the way it does, ChatGPT doesn't give me a full answer [...] when I am seeking a deeper understanding of what's going on" (P1)</i>
Difficulty in appropriately using genAI responses	Misleading/Confusing responses	Participants found genAI's responses to be misleading or confusing.	<i>"It outputted sensible looking code but it didn't match my instructions, leading to confusion" (P5)</i>
	Hard to adapt to needs/context	Participants struggled to adapt genAI provided solutions to their needs or context.	<i>"I don't feel confident even after spending time learning prompt engineering to how to make it generate content that fits all the needs" (P3)</i>
	Hard to modify or generalize AI responses	Participants struggled to modify and generalize genAI's responses.	<i>"Sometimes it would give me the solution to the prompt which will be specific to that one instance and its responses would be very hard to generalize or modify to include all cases" (P3)</i>
	Hard to verify AI responses	Participants found it hard to verify genAI's responses (explanations, answers, solutions)	<i>"I did face difficulties in using AI, sometimes it is not really accurate, it gave me answers but I didn't know how to verify them so I couldn't be sure of them" (P4)</i>
AI ISSUES (FAULTS)			
Reasoning Flaws	Logic loops	Instances where genAI got stuck in a repetitive cycle of responses or reasoning loops without progressing towards a correct solution.	<i>"Sometimes AI will give you the wrong piece of code, and then you'll try it. It doesn't work, and it'll be like, oh, I see the mistake and then will give you the same piece of code back...you're like in a loop where it just goes back and forth and doesn't lead anywhere" (P7)</i>
	Self-Contradiction	Instances where genAI self-contradicted itself or made assertions that negated its own premise/initial conditions.	<i>"I really felt annoying when I used [ChatGPT] for a multiple choice question where the correct answer is D but it gives me that A is right. When asked whether it is sure, it changes to D, and on asking again it changes to B. It's really indecisive even when I try to correct it. It keeps switching answers and this is a huge problem that I face" (P4)</i>
Response quality issues	Incomplete assistance	GenAI offered incomplete assistance to the participants.	<i>"ChatGPT was not as helpful as I expected it to be [...] I needed a precise explanation for each step and it wasn't providing me with that, as it would skip through certain steps" (P14)</i>
	Limited help on specifics	GenAI provided insufficient detail or depth when addressing specific topics, concepts, or areas,	<i>"If I wanted to know why a procedure operates the way it does, rather than what I would envision in my head to be a better way, generative AI didn't give me a full answer which was annoying as I wanted a deeper understanding of what was going on" (P1)</i>
	Incompatible Response	GenAI solutions were incompatible with students' problems or needs	<i>"I was working in node and asked [ChatGPT] something related to it, and it gave me a response that worked in node 16 but I was on node 18. So, I had to turn to like Google to kind of figure out why is it not working. But ChatGPT didn't really express or make it clear that it was talking about a specific version. It just dumped it on me as the correct answer." (P3)</i>
	Inconsistent/Incorrect Response	GenAI responses were incorrect, failing to provide accurate information, or inconsistent, offering varying answers to the same question or problem.	<i>"Sometimes [ChatGPT] used to provide wrong information or it used to give me different answers for the same question which was time consuming, so I had to also Google the information to verify." (P9)</i>
	Suboptimal responses	GenAI did not provide the optimal or efficient options to address problems.	<i>"[ChatGPT] doesn't do the things the correct way. It was harder for me to learn, or pick up concepts because the things that it was giving me were not entirely the best solution, because it gave unoptimal ways of writing code." (P3)</i>
	Non-generalizable Solution	Solutions provided by genAI were often hard coded or were not generalizable to similar problems or scenarios.	<i>"It was hard to build general purpose software with GPT [...] it provided code that was not really reusable" (P3)</i>
Deceptive Behavior	Hallucination	GenAI generated information or data that was entirely fabricated or unrelated to the input or reality and provides convincing explanations.	<i>"Sometimes [ChatGPT] gives baseless answers with convincing explanations... I never end up learning from it because there's a debate between what the AI said and the original source, and I don't know why something is correct" (P3)</i>
	Confirmation Bias	GenAI tends to favor information that confirms pre-existing beliefs or ideas, regardless of their validity.	<i>"In my experience, I have found instances where AI was not 100% right and wont take up any accountability and would just apologize and agree to whatever I am saying" (P4)</i>
GenAI neglects students' context/preferences	Neglects students' preferences	GenAI neglected students' preferences while providing a solution	<i>"After I explained repeatedly that I needed to optimize my script without changing external dependencies, the solutions suggested by Bard and ChatGPT still involved alternate libraries" (P9)</i>
	Misinterprets students' problem	GenAI misinterpreted students' problems or issues.	<i>"When you ask ChatGPT or any other genAI to not do something a particular way, it does it anyways" (P16)</i>
	Misguided guardrails	GenAI's rigid templates or restrictions led to generic responses, ignoring the unique context of the request.	<i>"It is frustrating when it doesn't want to give me output because it thinks it is a terms of use issue without evaluating my context" (P5)</i>
AI ISSUES (GAPS)			
	Limited for in-depth understanding of concepts	GenAI's assistance falls short in providing the necessary depth for a comprehensive understanding of concepts.	<i>"It was in CS362 class...GPT or Bard didn't provide a specific reason that I felt was good enough or believable on why [a test case] should be designed that way" (P2)</i>

Scaffolding gaps	Lacks visualization support* (in free versions (ChatGPT, Bing) as of 2024)	GenAI lacks visualization support for comprehension of concepts.	<i>"It is limited to text and not very helpful for visual learners. On the other end, I can go to a YouTube video which will be more helpful" (P16)</i>
	Gives out direct answer	GenAI has a tendency to give out solutions or answers directly that hinders learning a concept step-by-step.	<i>"ChatGPT does take away from my learning, just because it gives me that immediate answer without me having to find it. I wait before I ask a super big question just so I can think about it before I see a direct answer" (P12).</i>
Gaps in programming support	Inadequate debugging support	GenAI struggles to assist with debugging code, identifying, and resolving errors.	<i>"I have noticed that [ChatGPT] doesn't always help in the debugging functions or programs in general which it misinterprets and goes wrong. It's not really able to pinpoint what's wrong and then I'm having to go do that myself" (P10)</i>
	Gaps in orchestrating code	GenAI struggles to provide solutions/manage code requiring orchestration—where multiple codebases, services, or processes need to be coordinated effectively.	<i>"GPT or copilot doesn't know about the structure of your project and all the code in it and so it can't make informed global decisions. It'll make local decisions since it struggles to orchestrate code from different functions, files, or services together" (P7)</i>
	Unsuitability for complex programming	GenAI struggles to help in complex programming tasks constricted by its limitations (eg: limited working memory, outdated knowledge)	<i>"Working with ChatGPT or using GPT generated code for bigger projects or large apps is hard, it can break the codebase" (P4)</i>
IMPACTS			
Impact on learning	Learning wrong information	Participants reported learning wrong information on using genAI for learning.	<i>"generative AI gives wrong information...I had to unlearn what AI said and relearn it using YouTube" (P1)</i>
	Incomplete understanding	Participants reported having incomplete understanding of concepts on using genAI for learning.	<i>"I am not able to use AI to wrestle with the ideas in the way I like to learn and understand the reasoning behind things. Using genAI is just like being told what to do, [...] I don't like that" (P1)</i>
Impact on Task	Figure things out on own	Participants reported having to navigate or figure out things on their own when genAI didn't provide appropriate or complete help.	<i>"GPT struggled to give an answer that worked or explain why it didn't work, it kept going back and back [...] I ended up doing it again from scratch using a different resource" (P12)</i>
	Slows down	Participants reported being delayed on their tasks because of they spend time deciphering incomplete or irrelevant genAI advice	<i>"ChatGPT didn't really give me a good answer. It went on for a long period of time, suggesting things that were similar but not useful to my project. I gave up and had to downsize that project" (P16)</i>
	Give up on task/topic	Participants reported abandoning specific tasks or topics, unable to proceed without the needed guidance.	<i>"For someone new, AI won't work, it would cause roadblocks and they would give up lacking an assumption of what it can be used for and what not" (P12)</i>
Impact on self	Overreliance	Instances of overreliance reported by participants, being dependent on genAI for solutions.	<i>"It is tempting to trust it blindly. Starting out, I often became too dependent on it for how to code and find the solution to the problem" (P15)</i>
	Frustration	Participants reported instances of feeling frustrated due to interactions with genAI	<i>"It wasn't helpful because it made false assumptions about the codebase [...] the provided code was profoundly unhelpful, I couldn't modify it as they were very different from what I needed. It was very frustrating and just hopeless." (P15)</i>
	Self Doubt	Instances of self doubt reported by participants, where they doubted their own abilities or approach in using genAI.	<i>"My friends can use it well, but I can't...I am worried I would be left behind when it replaces Google search and I don't know how to talk to it." (P4)</i>
Impact on Adoption	Distrust	Participants reported distrust in genAI solutions, making them skeptical of its reliability and usefulness.	<i>"I don't trust generative AI for any critical work, it doesn't provide proper justifications; it's more like a predictive text answer that is hard to verify". (P2)</i>
	Steer away from AI	Participants reported avoiding using genAI tools altogether, preferring traditional methods or other resources.	<i>"I don't use it for any implementations because I don't consider it to be something I have written...And I think until the boundaries become clearer on whether it's right to use it or not, I am not comfortable using it for work that I have to claim as my own" (P10)</i>